

Title: GEOMETRIC MODELLING AND DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF A ROBOTIC GRIPPER USING META-HEURISTIC OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

Name: Golak Bihari Mahanta^{1, a}, Bibhuti Bhusan Biswal^{2, a}, BBVL Deepak^{3, a}, Amruta Rout^{4, a}, G Balamurali^{5, a}

Affiliation: Department of Industrial Design, NIT Rourkela, Odisha-769008, India

INTRODUCTION:

In this twenty firsts centuries competitive environment, for mass production and quality products industrial robots are playing a significant role. With the advancement of technologies, various methods are used to control the gripper. For performing the grasping and manipulation tasks such as pick place, role of a robot gripper mechanism is crucial. Robotic grippers are used in the simple, precision, high accuracy and repetitive work like in automobile industries, aircraft, and micro-nano fabrication industries, etc. Industrial robots are mainly having manipulator to interact with the environment, energy source and to control the robot computer controller. End effector or robotic gripper is a part of the manipulator which uses to hold the objects. Various types of gripper designed to handle the object and operated using electrical, pneumatic types of energy source. Grippers are designed considering the physical constraints and a different design for various processes. Cutkosky [1] carried out a study on the human grasp choice according to the grasp taxonomy and proposed various types of the model and design the grasp. Ceccarelli et al. [2] used Cartesian coordinate's methodology for the dimensional synthesis of gripper mechanisms. Chen [3] summarized the various gripping mechanism of the industrial robots. Osyczka [4] proposed a method to solve the robot gripper design problem by converting it into a multi-objective optimization problem. He considered various configuration and obtained the optimized designed parameters for the robotic gripper. Osyczka et al. [5] formulated a multicriteria optimization problem of the robotic gripper in which by using min-max and genetic algorithm design parameters obtained. Osyczka et al. [6] solved the nonlinear multi-criteria optimization problem such as Interval objective function, beam design problem and Robot gripper design using GA. Krenich [7] solved the design optimization problem of a robotic gripper using an evolutionary algorithm and weighted min-max approach. Abu-Zitar et al. [8] proposed evolutionary programming method to solve the nonlinear frictional gripper problem in robotic grasping considering three finger contact. Osyczka et al. [9] addressed various types of multicriteria design optimization problem such as gripper design, multiple clutch break design and shaft design using evolutionary algorithms. Abu Zitar et al. [10] proposed a novel method using ant colony optimization to find the optimum grasping force on a rigid body. They considered three finger contact and solved the nonlinear problem. Saravanan et al. [11] used an intelligent technique such as genetic algorithm, sorting algorithm, differential evolution, etc., to find the best dimensions for the gripper, i.e., optimum geometric dimensions of a robotic gripper which is used to the manufacturing of the gripper. They considered 3- configurations for the robotic gripper. Formulated five different objective functions and various constrained condition and solve the design optimization problem by using Multi-objective Genetic Algorithm (MOGA), Elitist Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) and Multiobjective Differential Evolution (MODE). Zaki et al. [12] designed an intelligent gripper using ANFIS and solve for the developed criteria. Datta et al. [13] proposed an objective function used to obtain

the optimized geometric configuration of the robotic gripper which minimizes the difference between the maximum and minimum gripping force. They solve the problem using NSGA-II. Rao et al. [14] formulated three robot gripper configuration as [11] and solved it by using TLBO and compare the results. They show that their algorithm performs better to get the results. In the following section a brief study of the used meta-heuristics is given.

AIM:

Robotic gripper plays a key player in the industrial robotics application such as pick and place, assembly, etc., and it is necessary to design and develop the best possible robotic gripper which needs a lot of mathematical formulation as well as analysis. In this paper, geometric modelling of a robotic gripper is proposed and the optimized design parameters of the robotic gripper using various meta-heuristics techniques. The proposed system was solved in two step methodology as geometric modelling and objective function for the gripper is formulated keeping all the environmental constraints. The developed objective function of the robotic gripper is a complex, constraint optimization problem and the objective is to determine the optimum force extracted by the robot gripper on the surface of a grasped rigid object under geometrical and functional constraints. Seven decision variables are chosen to develop the geometric model and the proposed objective function for the robotic gripper is solved using different metaheuristic techniques such as artificial bee colony (ABC), Firefly Algorithm (FA), Invasive Weed Optimization (IWO), and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). Effect of the controlling parameters for the metaheuristics algorithm on decision variables of the robotic gripper is thoroughly investigated. The Pareto-optimal solutions are investigated to establish some meaningful relationships between the objective functions and decision variable.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The robot configurations considered in this paper for the analysis is originally formulated by Osyczka [5], and detailed description for the same is mention below. The developed multi-objective function or fitness function uses seven decision variable such as $X = [a, b, c, e, f, l, \delta]^T$. The decision variable $a, b, c, e, f, and l$ are the dimensions of the gripper and δ is the joint angle between elements b and c of the gripper. The actuating force used to operate the gripper is P and the angle of the link b w.r.t horizontal reference line is β and angle of the link a w.r.t horizontal reference line is α . For holding the object with the help of the robotic gripper, it is necessary to give some gripping force (F_k) to hold the object without slipping.

The objective functions are formulated above consists of the decision variable of the robotic gripper i.e. link length and the joint angles ($X = [a, b, c, e, f, l, \delta]^T$) and on the displacement z which is the displacement of the actuator. The minimum value for the actuator displacement is 0 when it is in initial position and maximum value at Z_{max} . The corresponding force variation with respect to the displacement is shown in the Fig. 2, which shows that maximum force when $z = 0$ and minimum when $z = Z_{max}$.

Fig. 2. Variation of the force w.r.t displacement z

By considering all criteria, the objective function is developed as follows:

$$f_1(x) = F_x(x, 0) - F_x(x, Z_{max}) \quad f_2(x) = \frac{P}{F(x, Z_{max})} \quad (5)$$

The above said objective function having the constraints equation and are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g1(x) &= Y_{min} - y(x, Z_{max}) \geq 0, & g5(x) &= (a + b)^2 - l^2 - e^2 \geq 0, \\ g2(x) &= y(x, Z_{max}) \geq 0, & g6(x) &= (l - Z_{max})^2 + (a - e)^2 - b^2 \\ g3(x) &= y(x, 0) - Y_{max} \geq 0, & & \geq 0, \\ g4(x) &= YG - y(x, 0) \geq 0, & g7(x) &= l - Z_{max} \geq 0, \\ & & g8(x) &= \min_z Fk(x, z) - FG \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The range of the seven decision variable by using which the objective function formulated are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 10 &\leq a \leq 250, \\ 10 &\leq b \leq 250, \\ 100 &\leq c \leq 300, \\ 0 &\leq e \leq 50, \\ 10 &\leq f \leq 250, 100 \leq l \leq 300, 1.0 \leq \delta \leq 3.14 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The geometric parameters used in the constraints equation for the objective function are: Y_{min} is the minimal dimension of the object to be grasped = 50 mm; YG is the maximum gripper ends displacement = 150 mm; Y_{max} is the maximum size of the object to be grasped = 100 mm; Z_{max} is the maximum displacement of the actuator = 100 mm; and the actuating force of the gripper, $P = 100$ N.

The methodology to use accelerated PSO to obtain the optimal value of the geometric parameters of the robotic gripper is illustrated in a flow chart as shown in Fig. 4. After obtaining the objective function algorithm is used to obtain the best geometric configuration for the robotic gripper. All the necessary parameters are initialized (α , β , number of population, number of

iteration, etc.). Evaluate the fitness for each population using Eq. (1-6). Then, check whether maximum iteration achieved or best solution found. Either of the above achieved, then displaced the output as the global best which is the best solution for the decision variables.

Fig. 3. Proposed Methodology

RESULTS:

For checking the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, a number of simulations are conducted. For the first case, the parameters used for the simulation is as follows: Population size=50, Maximum number of generations=150. All the link length of the grippers is in mm, and the angle between the links a and b is in radian. For simulation, the methodology proposed here using meta-heuristics technique to solve for the robotic configuration was implemented using MATLAB 2014a on an Intel i7 2600, CPU 3.40GHz personal computer with 4 GB of RAM. After successfully implementing the meta-heuristics algorithm to solve the gripper optimization problem, the variation of the obtained output is shown in the Fig. 5. In Fig. 5, (a) shows the behavior of the decision variable (seven) with respect to iteration of the algorithm for ABC techniques, (b) shows the variation for IWO technique, (c) for PSO technique, and (d) for FA techniques. Decision variable a takes around 65 iterations to converge in all the methods.

Remaining decision variable for the gripper configurations converges in between 30-40 iterations and gave the desired results.

Fig. 4. Variation of decision variable w.r.t iteration number

Initially, there is a rapid variation of the decision variables. But around iteration number 60, all the variables are converged to a fixed value giving the best results. Hence, in this case, we varied the applied force, iteration number keeping the value of α and β constant and record the change in the decision variable and force value in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 for meta-heuristic technique ABC, IWO, PSO and FA respectively. Objective function f_1 & f_2 are in N. all the decision variable (a, b, c, e, f, l) are in mm and δ is in radian.

Table 1: Optimal obtained parameters for ABC algorithm

P(N)	f_1	f_2	a	b	c	e	f	l	δ
150	168.8	3.04	149.9	149.8	131.36	5.6	42.85	101.4	2.19
160	169.9	3.4	149.8	149.8	130.1	6.6	44.80	106.9	3.15
170	178.4	3.9	148.5	150.0	135.9	5.9	42.4	102.7	2.42

Table 2: Optimal obtained parameters for IWO algorithm

P (N)	f_1	f_2	a	b	c	e	f	l	δ
150	178.5	3.04	149.7	150.0	132.5	5.2	41.8	101.4	3.1
160	179.1	3.4	148.3	149.8	130.3	5.6	44.2	106.7	3.3
170	178.8	3.9	148.5	149.3	133.8	5.9	44.4	107.0	3.5

Table 3: Optimal obtained parameters for PSO algorithm

P	f_1	f_2	a	b	c	e	f	l	δ
150	158.8	3.24	147.3	150.0	133.3	6.6	42.8	101.4	3.09
160	159.2	3.76	147.8	149.8	133.5	6.1	44.3	106.9	3.1
170	160.3	3.9	148.5	150.0	135.3	5.9	42.4	102.7	3.4

Table 4: Optimal obtained parameters for FA algorithm

P	f_1	f_2	a	b	c	e	f	l	δ
150	158.8	3.04	148.9	148.8	130.9	5.9	40.8	102.4	3.2
160	159.8	3.45	149.1	148.3	130.2	5.6	42.3	104.1	3.34
170	158.4	3.99	149.9	150.0	135.7	5.89	44.4	106.9	3.45

Computational time taken by the techniques are recorded and compared among themselves. From the Fig. 5., we concluded that the Firefly Algorithm take minimum time (21 sec) for solving the problem and Invasive Weed algorithm takes more time to compute the problem.

Fig. 5. Computational Time

CONCLUSIONS:

In the present work, four meta-heuristics algorithm used to solve for the multi-objective design optimization of robot grippers and performances is recorded. From the simulation results, it was found that the in all algorithms around 60 iterations the decision variable converged and result obtained. By changing the force P, the output of the proposed system recorded. Firefly algorithm able to solve the proposed method within 21 sec, so it is considered as the most suitable algorithm for the proposed multi-objective gripper mechanism. The obtained set of optimal dimensions of the robotic gripper can be used to develop the real time gripper

KEYWORDS:

Multi objective optimization; Gripper force; Meta-heuristics; Algorithm.

BIOGRAPHY:

Golak Bihari Mahanta He is currently a Research Scholar with the NIT Rourkela, India. His research interests include synthesis of mechanisms, evolutionary robotics, multi objective optimization, gripper design, soft robotics, and investigation of advanced metaheuristics for the robotics grasping and gripper optimization.

Bibhuti Bhusan Biswal He is graduated in mechanical engineering from UCE, Burla, India in 1985. Subsequently he completed his M.Tech, and Ph.D. from Jadavpur University, Kolkata. He joined the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering at UCE Burla from 1986 and continued till 2004 and then joined National Institute of Technology, Rourkela as a professor and currently he is the professor and head of Department of Industrial Design. He has been actively involved in various research projects and published more than 300 papers at National and International levels. His areas of research interest include industrial robotics, FMS, computer integrated manufacturing, automation, and maintenance engineering. He was a visiting professor at MSTU, Moscow and a visiting scientist at GIST, South Korea.